

Electrothermal Atomic Absorption Spectrometric Determination of Cadmium in Coal Fly Ash

SHUVENDU S BHATTACHARYYA, BANDANA MANDAL and ARABINDA K DAS*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104

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Cadmium is a by-product of zinc and lead mining and smelting, which are important sources of environmental pollution. Airborne cadmium in workplace environment, in rural and in urban areas, has been reported by Kneip *et al.*¹ In river sediment and coal fly ash, cadmium has been determined by GFAAS². Liquid chelating exchangers³ have been used for the separation and preconcentration of trace elements.

In the present work, cadmium has been separated by using a β -thioxoketone liquid chelating exchanger (RCOCH₂CSCCH₃). Electrothermal AAS has been used for the determination of cadmium in various coal fly ash samples. This separation technique has been used for the avoidance of matrix interferences.

Results and Discussion

Optimisation of electrothermal furnace conditions : Temperature and times of different stages (drying, charring, atomisation etc.) were investigated and optimised. In the extraction process, quantitative extraction of Cd was found to be in the pH range 8.5-10.0. The working pH was fixed at 8.8 using trisbuffer. 100% extraction of cadmium could be attained by using pentyl alcohol.

Cadmium (45 μ g) was separated from binary mixtures of various ions with tolerance limit of interferences (in μ g) within an error of $\pm 2\%$; Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺ (10 each); Cr⁶⁺, Zn²⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, MoO₄²⁻, PO₄³⁻ (5 each), SiO₃²⁻ (3), Mn²⁺ (2.5), VO₂²⁺ (2), Pb²⁺ (1.5), Al³⁺, Fe³⁺ (1 each), Ti⁴⁺ (0.2), SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, Cl⁻ (10 each), Cadmium (45 μ g) was also separated from several synthetic mixtures (Table 1).

The proposed method was applied to determine cadmium in various coal fly ash samples, and also in the marine sediment reference material and the results (Table 2) are comparable to the certified values. In order to verify the reliability of the method spiked recoveries of Cd were performed with satisfactory results.

The nature of the extracted species was determined from the slope value of the plot of log *D* against pH, which is 1.8. It transpires that the extractable complex is Cd(LCE)₂ and the extraction mechanism may be represented as

where subscript *o* and *a* represent organic and aqueous phases respectively.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM IN (45 ng) IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Sl no	Composition (ng)	% Error
1	Mg ²⁺ (3000) + Al ³⁺ (2500) + SO ₄ ²⁻ (5500)	+0.38
2	Ti ⁴⁺ (500) + Zn ²⁺ (2000) + SO ₄ ²⁻ (2500)	-1.85
3	Fe ³⁺ (1000) + Ca ²⁺ (5200) + Zn ²⁺ (2000)	+1.52
4	Al ³⁺ (2000) + SO ₄ ²⁻ (2000) + Na ⁺ (10,000)	+0.16
5	Mn ²⁺ (2000) + Cr ⁶⁺ (2000) + VO ₂ ²⁺ (2000)	-0.18

Experimental

A Shimadzu AA-646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer equipped with an electrothermal furnace atomiser (GFA-4A) and an autosampling unit (AIU-1) was used. A cadmium hollow cathode lamp was used as a resonance line source. Instrumental operating conditions were as follows : wave

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM IN COAL FLY ASH

Fly ash sample	Cd found ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	
	Without separation	Present method
KTPP-2	1.56	0.58
KTPP-3	1.61	0.61
BTPP-4	5.98	0.66
BTPP-5	5.63	0.82
DPL-1	5.82	1.43
DPL-2	16.55	3.42
DPL-4	6.06	0.88
Reference material ^a (MESS-1, NRC)	2.90	0.66

^aCertified value, $0.59 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$.

length, 228.8 nm; lamp current, 8 mA; slit-width, 0.19 nm; mode, BGC (D_2 lamp); sample size, 10 μl ; expansion, X1. In the furnace programme the ashing and atomisation temperature were optimised to 200 and 1300° respectively. Argon was used as a purge gas. A β -thioxoketone liquid chelating exchanger (LCE) was prepared⁴. A 0.1 M ethanolic solution of the exchanger was used. Cadmium solution ($5738 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by dissolving $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Merck) in double-distilled water and standardised⁵. All other reagents used were of analytical grade. Marine sediment, MESS-1 (NRC, Canada) was used as a reference material.

The coal fly ash samples were collected from different thermal power plants of West Bengal (India) : (i) Durgapur Project Limited (DPL), (ii) Bandel Thermal Power Plant (BTPP) and (iii) Kolaghat Thermal Power Plant (KTPP). The dried (110°) powdered sample (100.00 mg each) was taken in a platinum crucible and silica was removed by using HF in a fume-chamber. The residue was mixed with 10-times excess of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (A.R., B.D.H.), fused over a Bunsen flame and heated red-hot for 15 min.

The fused mass was cooled and taken into 10% H_2SO_4 (v/v) by warming in a steam-bath. The resulting solution was made upto 10 ml. The reference material was taken into solution by the same procedure. For the preparation of process blank, the steps described above for the preparation of fly ash and sediment samples were followed. Ten μl process blank was used.

General procedure : An aqueous solution (0.2 ml) containing $114.76 \text{ ng ml}^{-1}$ Cd was taken and its pH was adjusted to 8.8. It was then treated with tris-buffer (2.0 ml) of pH 8.8 and 0.1 M LCE (1.8 ml) and the mixture was shaken for 5 min with pentyl alcohol and allowed to settle for 5 min. The organic phase was separated and stripped with 0.1 M HNO_3 . Then the aqueous phase was made upto 10.0 ml. Ten μl of the solution was injected into the electrothermal furnace and the amount of Cd estimated from the calibration graph.

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